

Adversarial samples of a trained convolutional neural network model

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Abstract: Deep neural networks are vulnerable to adversarial samples which are usually crafted by adding perturbations to the correct input. Therefore, adversarial samples can be used to identify and evaluate the robustness of a trained model before it is launched. In this work, we introduce two methods to generate adversarial images for a CNN model that was trained to perform surgical tool classification in laparoscopic videos. Both methods proved to be effective to fool the model, but show some drawbacks.

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I. Introduction

Deep neural networks (DNNs) have shown effectiveness in many applications; however, they are vulnerable to adversarial attacks which are generated by small perturbations on the legitimate samples. Some perturbations are imperceptible to human vision but lead a trained model to wrong predictions and decrease its usefulness. These issues turn to be more significant when DNNs are launched for some safety-critical domains with high financial and safety risk [1,2,3]. Therefore, generating adversarial examples creates an opportunity to identify the vulnerability of the models and improve their robustness by providing additional training samples [1].

Recently, many approaches for generating adversarial examples have been proposed, such as the fast gradient sign method (FGSM) [4], the iterative fast gradient sign method (I-FGSM) [5], the momentum iterative fast gradient sign method (MI-FGSM) [1], the distributional adversarial attack (DAA), perturbations based on L0, L2, L ∞ norm distance metrics, the saliency map approach, DeepFool, and generative adversarial networks (GANs) [6].

Among these approaches, a few can be used to generate a target-class adversarial example. For instance, the target-FGSM method can decrease the adversarial loss between predicted class and target class [6], or use forward

Figure 1: The original image(left) is correctly classified as hook (class 3). A flipped image(right) misclassified by the trained model as specimen bag (class 7, the confidence score assigned to class 7 is 0.97).

derivative to construct adversarial saliency maps to map input perturbations to output variations [2]. In this paper, we present two methods for generating adversarial samples. For our experiments, we target a convolutional neural network (CNN) that was trained to perform surgical tool classification in laparoscopic videos.

II. Material and methods

The AlexNet [7] model was fine-tuned to perform tool classification in laparoscopic images. To simplify the implementation, only one-tool images were included in this study. Therefore, a dataset of one-label images was extracted from the Cholec80 dataset [8] and used for evaluation. The derived dataset contains 80,190 images, and it was randomly divided into (25,000) for training and (55,190) for testing the CNN.

II.I. Image flip

Adversarial samples were simply generated by flipping the images row-wise and column-wise. The new images were then provided to the CNN model to evaluate its robustness against such a simple manipulation of the original images. A small test set that contains 700 images (100 images per class) was used.

II.II. Linear interpolation

To generate adversarial samples for a target class and to gain some intuition into the “distance” of classes, two images were selected. The selected images were belonging to different tool classes (first and second images classes termed as class A and class B respectively) and were correctly classified by the CNN model. The class activation map that shows regions of the image engaged in the classification were visualized [9]. The adversarial samples were then generated using linear interpolation as following:

- The linear interpolation of two inputs is defined as:

$$x^* = t * x_1 + (1 - t) * x_2, \quad t \in [0,1]$$

Where x^* is the generated adversarial image, x_1 and x_2 are the two selected images.

- Only the regions that were distinctly involved in the classification from both images were included. Therefore, these regions were extracted at different thresholds of the gradient class activation map (0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8).
- The output of the previous step was used to replace the corresponding image area in the original image with the target class.
- The generated adversarial sample has the same background of the image with the original class.
- The CNN classification performance was evaluated for 100 different values of t .

Figure 2: The classification of the generated image changed at $t = 0.53$.

Figure 3: The generated image at $t = 0.53$. The noised area in the object is the interpolation result of original and target class.

III. Results and discussion

The robustness CNN model was firstly evaluated against image flipping. The classification accuracy of the model with the original test set was 88.14%. The classification performance of the model decreased obviously when it was tested with the flipped images. The accuracies achieved for the row-wise and column-wise flipped datasets were 48.86% and 66.86% respectively. The drop of classification accuracies reflects the sensitivity of the CNN model to any changes in the input image.

The interpolation approach was evaluated at different thresholds to extract attention regions of the images and at different interpolation thresholds (t). Fig. 2 shows classification probabilities of class A and class B at 0.8

threshold of attention region. As can be seen from the figure, the classification was changed at $t=0.53$. Table 1 shows t values at which the classification was changed for different thresholds of the attention regions. In this reported case both classes were stable and the critical flip point was around 0.5. But the generated images have a clearly noisy tool area which makes them abnormal and easy to perceive by human vision. (see Fig. 3)

Table 1: The value of interpolation threshold (t) at which the classification of the CNN was changed from class A to class B for different attention regions threshold

Threshold of attention regions	t threshold
0	0.45
0.2	0.43
0.4	0.42
0.6	0.46
0.8	0.53

IV. Conclusions

In this work, the CNN robustness was investigated by introducing two simple approaches for generating adversarial samples. Further work, is needed for evaluation of these and other methods to generate adversarial images.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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